

Modelling of a Portable Decentralised Anaerobic Digester for the Production of Biogas from Cattle Dung and its Analysis Using GCMS

Guntheti G D D Sree Vajran¹, M. Lashmeetha Manaswini², Pulletikurthi Lokeshwari³,
N. Prathusha⁴, Nikitha Narayanan⁵, D. Metilda Rosalin^{6*}

^{1,2,3,4,5,6}Department of Genetics and Biotechnology, Bhavan's Vivekananda College of Science,
Humanities & Commerce Sainikpuri, Secunderabad- 500094

*Email: metilda2324@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Modelling and development of decentralized anaerobic digestion systems are the key to enabling small-scale and on-site biogas production from organic waste. A portable decentralised anaerobic digester was modelled, fabricated, and experimentally analysed with respect to biogas generation using cattle dung as the main substrate. The digester model was constructed with a plastic bottle reactor with an intravenous (IV) tubing kit built in to allow control of the gas collection. Fresh cattle dung mixed with water to become a homogenous slurry and introduced into the digester, which was airtight sealed using wax in order to keep anaerobic conditions and prevent gas leakage.

The system was run under ambient conditions, with incubation time varying from 30 to 90 days with respect to the weather. Biogas generation was first verified by fire by the flame test, in which the presence of combustible gas is observed. The produced biogas was further characterized with the help of gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The total ion chromatogram (TIC) showed the presence of several volatile and semi-volatile compounds such as dimethylamine, 1-octadecanethiol and tetradecanoic acid and other aliphatic and sulfur-containing compounds related to anaerobic microbial degradation during anaerobic digestion.

The modelling and experimental validation show that the developed portable decentralised digester has the ability for effective biogas production through a simple and low-cost configuration. The proposed system provides a viable solution to decentralized renewable energy production and organic waste treatment. Furthermore, the study contributes to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being) through improved sanitation, SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) by enabling renewable biogas production, and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) by promoting innovative and scalable digestion systems.

Keywords: Anaerobic digester, Biogas production, Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

1. INTRODUCTION

The ever growing energy demand in the world, especially due to the exploitation of fossil fuel reserves and the resulting environmental concerns have necessitated the dire necessity to find sustainable and renewable resources of energy(Shahzad & Umair, 2012). Traditional energy systems significantly contribute to green-house gases emissions, air pollution, and climate change that cause severe threats to environmental balance and population well-being(Carter, 2019). Simultaneously, inefficient management of organic waste, especially livestock waste, is also a problematic issue in rural and peri-urban locations(Prasad,2019). These interwoven problems point to the need to adopt concomitant strategies that tackle the problems of clean energy generation and green waste management(Vlachokostas, 2020).

Anaerobic digestion for biogas has been reported to be an easy and ecologically friendly approach to transform organic waste into a useful energy source.(Ibrahim, 2016). Cattle dung in form, among other feedstocks is readily accessible, particularly in the farmlands and has an appropriate organic composition as well as microbial profiles which are conducive to anaerobic digestion. Mostly, the biogas is composed of methane and carbon dioxide, which can be successfully used to cook, heat water, and generate electricity, whereas the residual by-product of the digestion process can be implemented as a successful bio-fertilizer with many nutrients (Kumar et al. 2022). Hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis are the four consecutive and interdependent stages of anaerobic digestion(He, 2025). Complex organic matter undergoes hydrolysis to simple soluble compounds, which are in turn converted into volatile fatty acids, alcohols, hydrogen and carbon dioxide during acidogenesis and acetogenesis stages. At the last stage of methanogenesis, acetate, hydrogen and carbon dioxide are transformed to methane-enriched biogas by methanogenic archaea. With the above advantages, the biogas technology is not widely adopted in large scale due to the high cost of capital, infrastructure demands, and use of the centralized system(Gonzalez-Fernandez, 2015).

Here, the decentralized and portable anaerobic digesters would be an option to the traditional big biogas plants. They facilitate treating organic waste on the spot, secure a decrease in vehicle transportation requirements, energy loss, and increase accessibility for households, small farms, and rural communities. Portable digesters can be considered especially advantageous to the resource-constrained settings because of their low prices, their simplicity in the way they operate and their flexibility(Alengebawy, 2024). Nonetheless, the workability and sustainability of small-scale digesters are highly tied to system design, operating condition and substrate, so they need to be systematically modelled and experimentally tested to be incorporated in a successful system and be scaled in the future(Issahaku, 2024).

The simplified digester arrangements on the use of readily available materials in the construction of the digesters have received more research attention in recent times, both at laboratory and field levels with respect to biogas production. When well closed, plastic-based digesters can

help preserve an anaerobic environment and allow microbes to thrive in order to produce biogas(Jameel et al., 2024). The primary gas collection elements, including tubing systems are included, which can be used to monitor gas production. However, there are still no rigorous studies on modelling, design, and chemical characterization of such portable decentralized systems, especially those that use sophisticated analytical procedures to verify biogas composition(Issahaku et al., 2024).

The biogas analysis through chemical analysis is very important in determining the pathway of anaerobic digestion and complements the quality of gas produced. A sound analytical method that can be employed to gain qualitative evidence of the process of anaerobic biodegradation is gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), as a reliable technique of analysing volatile and semi-volatile compounds that are present in biogas(Araujo et al., 2023).

The use of such techniques as evaluation of total ion chromatograms (TICs) helps to detect the presence of metabolic intermediates and degradation products, which is a much better validation of the formation of the biogas compared to simply using flame tests(Métivier et al., 2020).

As a result, the current work aims at modelling and experimental evaluation of the portable decentralized anaerobic digester to generate biogas using cattle dung. An elementary model of a digester was assembled with a reactor made of a plastic bottle coupled with an intravenous (IV) system of gathering gases and closed to maintain anaerobic conditions. The process of biogas generation was observed at an incubation time of 30-90 days, with the first confirmation being done by flame test. The resulting biogas underwent an additional analysis using GC-MS to determine typical compounds that were created due to the anaerobic digestion(Hassan et al., 2022).

The main aim of the research is to determine the viability of a low-cost, portable biogas-based system to generate energy at the decentralized community level and offer an analytical justification of biogas composition(Owhondah et al, 2019). Moreover, the study fits within the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), by enhancing hygiene and decreasing contact with untouched waste, SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) by advancing the creation of digestion systems which can be scalable and innovative, and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) by developing new and transformative digestion systems(Arora & Mishra, 2022).On the whole, the research contributes to the creation of sustainable, accessible and decentralized solutions to the production of renewable energy and management of organic waste(Rathore et al, 2022).

2. MATERIALS REQUIRED

1. Transparent plastic bottle of suitable capacity.
2. Fresh cow dung.
3. Fresh buffalo dung.

4. Distilled water.
5. An intravenous (IV) tubing kit .
6. Wax.
7. Soldering rod.
8. Detergent.
9. Bunsen burner / Lighter/ Matchbox .
10. Parafilm tape.
11. A beaker and a glass rod.
12. Adhesive.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Anaerobic digester preparation:

A bottle made of transparent plastic of an adequate size was taken and used as a batch-mode anaerobic digester. The bottle and cap were carefully washed and rinsed by using laboratory-grade detergent and distilled water, respectively before using them. The digester was then sterilized in order to eliminate any remaining contaminants and non-target microbes that may complicate anaerobic microbial growth. Such a step of sterilization was necessary to guarantee the controlled experiment conditions and to increase the reproducibility. The bottle was recorded to air-dry in aseptic conditions after sterilization and then further prepared in terms of subsequent modification and loading slurry (Ramos Suarez et al, 2023).

3.2. Preparation of Cattle Dung Slurry

The fresh cow dung and buffalo dung were also obtained differently, from a close source of livestock to ensure the availability of active anaerobic microbial communities. Dung samples were collected and manually homogenized and any foreign objects like rocks, straws and plant debris were eliminated. A 1:1 (w/v) mixture of each dung sample with clean water was taken to get a homogenous slurry of the right viscosity. Only 25% of the bottle was filled with the slurry. The reason behind such a dilution ratio was to add moisture needed so that there is enough content of microbes, better mobility of the microbes, and to ensure efficiency in anaerobic digestion. The resulting prepared slurries were directly transferred into different labelled sterilized digester bottles to limit any contact with atmospheric oxygen and, at the same time, maintain anaerobic conditions (Kiyasudeen et al., 2015).

3.3 Provision of Gas Outlet and Importing System:

The gas outlet and collection systems used were an intravenous (IV) set as it is flexible, available, and easily manageable. The bottle cap opening was made very small in the center and using a heated soldering rod, an opening was made on the top of the bottle cap with care so that

it is not too big. The opening was made and the IV tubing was carefully inserted into the opening so as to achieve a tight and secure fit. A permanent adhesive was also used to have a firm fixation of the tube upon the insertion area. This was then sealed up with hot molten wax to make the whole joint area airtight to avoid the loss of gases or entry of air in the atmosphere (Erraji et al., 2024).

After loading the slurry, an anaerobic environment in the digester was maintained by removing the air trapped. The bottle top was then the tightest one and the bead of the bottle and the bottle top were also sealed using molten wax to strengthen the airtight cap. The IV tubing was also closed at syringe end so that in the course of incubation, there would be no loss of gas (Erraji et al., 2021).

3.4 Conditions of Anaerobic Digestion and Incubation:

After the full sealing of the digester, the bottle was shaken gently such that there was a homogeneous distribution of the slurry as well as the populations of the microbes across the substrates. The digester was then subject to the condition of the undisturbed incubation at the room temperature of the laboratory. The anaerobic digestion was left to develop in batch mode between 30 and 90 days, depending on the development and stabilization of the production of gases. During the incubation cycle, the digester was kept not disturbed so that there is no disturbance to the anaerobic conditions and also to avoid disturbance to the microbial consortia present in the biogas formation (Holm-Nielsen et al., 2009)

3.5 Confirmation of Biogas Formation:

Formation of biogas was first tested by means of a flame test. Gas pressure in the digester was carefully let out via the IV tube and fed into a source of flame under controlled conditions. The emergence of a blue stable flame was qualitative evidence of the existence of combustible gas that means successful production of biogas (Abdel-Hadi et al., 2009).

Besides the flame test, physical changes in the digester were also monitored as the incubation period was investigated. The initially pressurized bottle of plastic started its expansion, a few weeks after incubation, which is a sign that gases were formed inside the bottle. Between 45-60 days, the digester was in full distended condition, which once again ensured continuous production of biogas and pressure build-up in the closed system (Rajendran et al., 2012).

3.6 GC-MS Analysis of Biogas:

A qualitative method of analysing the chemical composition of the produced biogas was to use gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The sample of biogas was taken using the IV tubing with a gas-tight syringe and then put into the GC-MS device. A total ion chromatogram (TIC) was then determined and each of the compounds was identified by comparing the mass spectra with the standard libraries of connotations. The observed compounds were utilized to

explain the biochemical changes that took place in anaerobic digestion and confirm the production of biogas in the portable decentralized system(Mulat et al., 2015).

IMAGE 1 : COLLECTION OF COW DUNG.

IMAGE 2: COLLECTION OF BUFFALO DUNG.

IMAGE 3: PREPARING CATTLE DUNG SLURRY.

IMAGE 4: MIXING SLURRY UNIFORMLY.

IMAGE 5: POURING SLURRY INTO THE PLASTIC BOTTLE.

IMAGE 6: REMOVING THE AIR TRAPPED INSIDE THE DIGESTOR.

IMAGE 7: INCUBATING THE ANEROBIC DIGESTORS AT ROOM TEMPERATURE FOR 30-90 DAYS.

IMAGE 8: DIGESTORS COMPLETELY FILLED WITH BIOGAS AFTER ANEROBIC CULTURING FOR 45- 60 DAYS.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Flame test results:

Qualitative validation of biogas generation was done by flame test as represented in Image 9. The gaseous state was emptied in the digester, with a lot of care, and exposed to a source of fire under regulated parameters. When ignited, the emitted gas gave out a clear and consistent blue flame, which is a sign that it contained combustible gaseous elements. The blue flame is typical of biogas with a large content of methane and indicates a high rate of combustion with low amounts of soot (Ilminnafik et al., 2019). The fact that the flame remained stable and it was found to persist shows that adequate amounts of combustible gas were produced in the digester, admitting a sufficient amount of energy during the incubation period (Hosseini & Wahid, 2013). This empirical finding is a first-hand observation that proves the presence of anaerobic digestion and gas accumulation in the closed apparatus. The flame test and the overall growth of the digester bottle that is seen in the course of the incubation test indicate conclusively that the biogas was continuously produced in the portable decentralized anaerobic digester (Liberti et al., 2019). The flame test was an easy but effective preliminary test of biogas production before chemical characterization was done further with GC-MS (Ward et al., 2010).

IMAGE 9: FLAME TEST USING A LIGHTER (BLUE FLAME CONFIRMS BIOGAS PRESENCE).

IMAGE 10: FLAME TEST USING A BUNSEN BURNER (BLUE FLAME CONFIRMS BIOGAS PRESENCE).

4.2 Characterisation of biogas produced using GC-MS.

The gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of the sample was performed at the Central Analytical Facility (CAF), University College of Technology, Osmania University,

Hyderabad, India. The analysis was done with a Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 instrument. The sample with the name Biogas was injected with a volume of 1,0 uL as an amount of injection and the acquired total ion chromatogram (TIC) was obtained through approximately 0-15 minutes in retention time. Compound identification was determined by the comparison of the obtained mass spectra with standard reference libraries in the GC-MS system.

4.2.1 Chromatographic Observation.

The total ion chromatogram (TIC) shows several peaks of different retention time indicating the presence of a mixture of volatile and semi-volatile organic compounds in the analyzed sample. Most of the prominent peaks are seen at early and mid-retention times, indicating the predominance of relatively low to medium molecular weight compounds, with a few peaks at higher retention times indicating the presence of heavier organic constituents(Moniruzzaman et al., 2014).

4.2.2. Compounds Identified in the sample.

4.2.2.1 2-Heptanamine, 5-methyl-

(Retention time: 0.016 min; Area: 0.68%)

2 - Heptanamine, 5 - methyl - a low - molecular - weight aliphatic amine has been detected in trace quantities and is characterised by very early elution due to its high volatility. Its presence is an indicative result of the anaerobic degradation of the proteinaceous material and an indicator for active microbial degreasing of the nitrogen containing organic matter during digestion(Gounou et al., 2011).

4.2.2.2 1-Octadecanethiol (Retention time: 0.097 min; Area: 26.55%)

1-Octadecanethiol, an organic compound long chain sulfur, showed a large area of the peak, thus indicating a large content of sulfur in the sample. Such sulfurous compounds are generally produced by the transformation of the sulfur-bearing organics, and are responsible for the particular composition and the trace elemental sulfur profile of the generated gas (Appels et al., 2008).

4.2.2.3 Dimethylamine

(Retention time: 1.049 min; Area: 39.37%) The one that was most abundant in the analysis was dimethylamine. Being a highly volatile nitrogen-containing species, its dominance brings into play a rather large nitrogenous organic fraction produced by anaerobic decomposition of proteins and amino acids, thus proving very active metabolic pathways in the microbes (Batstone et al., 2002)

4.2.2.4 Tetradecanoic acid Myristic acid

(Retention time: 12.919 min; Area: 32.77%) The retention time of 16 carbon fatty acids, tetradecanoic acid (saturated long-chain fatty acid), because of the high molecular weight and low volatility. This compound is a representative of lipid decomposition products of anaerobic digestion and acts as a necessary intermediate product in the decomposition of complex fats (Weiland et al., 2010).

4.2.2.5 3-Isopropoxy-1,1,1,7,7,7-hexamethyl-3,5,5-tris(trimethylsiloxy) tetrasiloxane

(Retention time: 13.929 min; Area: 0.40%) The siloxane - based compound in question is a high moiety (molecular weight) silicon - containing molecule that is often detected in GC - MS analyses. Its presence points to the complexity of the composition of the gas-phase seen in the analysis and illustrates the need for detailed chemical characterisation (Ajhar et al. 2010).

4.2.2.6 Octane, 3,4,5,6-tetramethyl- (Retention time: 14.261 min; Area: 0.24%)

Octane, 3,4,5,6 - tetramethyl -, a branched aliphatic hydrocarbon, showed a higher retention time, which is associated with lower volatility and larger molecular stability. Such branched hydrocarbons are characteristic of stabilised organic fractions produced under anaerobic conditions and indicate advanced phases of organic matter transformation (Ahrens T and Weiland P2007).

Table 1. Classification of GC-MS-Identified Compounds and Their Functional Contributions in Anaerobic Digestion System

Category	Compounds Identified	Functional Contribution
Nitrogen-containing compounds (amines, amides, heterocycles)	Dimethylamine; 2-Heptanamine, 5-methyl-; Imidazole, 2-amino-5-[(2-carboxy)vinyl]-; Bicyclo[2.2.1]heptane-5-(ethyl-1-amine); Hydrazine, methyl-, oxalate; 2-Formylhistamine; Phenol, 4-(2-aminopropyl)-; 2H-Azepin-2-one, hexahydro-1-methyl-	These compounds are the product of the anaerobic decomposition of protein-rich organic matter. Their detection indicates active microbial metabolism and the production of volatile nitrogenous intermediates in the digestion process (An et al., 2024)
Fatty acids (saturated long-chain carboxylic acids)	Tetradecanoic acid; Pentadecanoic acid; Hexadecanoic acid; Octadecanoic acid; Eicosanoic acid	Fatty acids are important intermediates in the course of lipid hydrolysis and acidogenic transformations (Hidalgo et al., 2025). Their presence attests to the efficient reduction of lipid constituents and progressive stabilization of organic matter (Zhang et al., 2022)

Category	Compounds Identified	Functional Contribution
Sulfur-containing organic compounds	1-Octadecanethiol	Sulphur - containing compounds are the result of the transformation of materials containing organic sulphur. Their detection reflects ongoing cycling of sulfur under stable reducing conditions in the anaerobic environment(<i>W. Zhang et al., 2022</i>)
Hydrocarbons (branched and saturated alkanes)	Octane, 3,4,5,6-tetramethyl-; Octane, 2,3,3-trimethyl-; Hexane, 2,2,3,3-tetramethyl-	Branched hydrocarbons, which suggest stabilized non - polar organic fractions that are formed in consequent phases of anaerobic processing, as well as the molecular reconfiguration of complex substrates(<i>Rabus et al., 2016</i>)
Oxygen-containing organic compounds (alcohols, ethers, aldehydes, esters)	5-(Prop-2-enoxy)pentadecane; 10-Octadecenal; Pentanol, 4-methyl-2-propyl-; Hexane, 2,5-dimethoxy-2,5-dimethyl-; 4-Fluoro-1-methyl-5-carboxylic acid, ethyl ester; 18,19-Secoyohimban-19-oic acid methyl ester	Oxygenated compounds occur as intermediates in the course of multi-step anaerobic conversion of carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins and thus underscore the dynamic qualities of biochemical conversion pathways(<i>Jain & Kumar, 2026</i>)
Halogen-containing organic compounds	1-Iodo-2-methylundecane; 1,3-Dioxolane, 2-(5-bromopentyl)-; 4-Fluoro-1-methyl-5-carboxylic acid, ethyl ester	The presence of halogenated compounds is evidence of the chemical diversity of the anaerobic system and its ability to contain structurally complex organic molecules(<i>Lv et al., 2025b</i>)
Silicon-containing compounds (siloxanes and silanes)	Methylsilane; trimethylsiloxy-substituted tetrasiloxanes; octamethyl-tetrasiloxane; heptamethyl-bis(trimethylsiloxy)tetrasiloxane	Silicon-bearing compounds are symptomatic of the complexity of the gas phase composition, giving importance to analytical characterization for the complete description of the entire chemical composition.(<i>Dvorackova et al., 2025</i>).

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the conception, fabrication, and evaluation of a portable, decentralized anaerobic digester for biogas production from cattle dung, a renewable organic feedstock, was developed(Thongsri et al., 2025). A simple batch reactor was designed using a polyethylene bottle connected to an intravenous tubing set for hermetically sealing the system and easy gas

recovery. These results highlight how successful production of biogas is achievable using low-cost materials that otherwise can be readily obtained utilizing existing infrastructure in decentralized locations, supporting the appropriateness of using decentralized digestion platforms for small-scale and resource-limited settings (Colón et al., 2015)

Anaerobic digestion process was performed under static conditions for a period of 30-90 days. Progressive physical changes during incubation, including gradual expansion of the reactor with final complete inflation of the reactor at ~45-60 days, indicated a continuous accumulation of the gas (Khadka et al., 2022) The successful ignition in the flame test indicated the presence of combustible gas, which thus proved successful biogas generation within the digester system (Yusuf et al., 2020)

Qualitative characterization of the generated biogas by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC - MS) showed further and detailed insight into the chemical composition of the generated biogas and supported the occurrence of anaerobic biochemical transformations. The total ion chromatogram showed that there was a complex mixture of volatile compounds and semi-volatile compounds, over a large range of retention times. Early - eluting peaks were dominated by nitrogen-containing compounds with low molecular weights, especially dimethylamine, indicating a high degree of microbial degradation of nitrogenous organic matter (Yusuf et al., 2020) The presence of substances like medium- and long-chain fatty acids (tetradecanoic acid and other saturated fatty acids) is the result of lipid breakdown and transformation during the process of digestion. Sulfur-bearing compounds and branched hydrocarbons also underlined the variety of metabolic processes, which participate in the anaerobic process (Han et al., 2023)

Additional compounds such as oxygenated aliphatics, halogenated hydroxyls and branched alkanes were responsible for the overall chemical complexity of the gas mixture. Silicon-based compounds observed in the analysis were attributed to instrumental or sealing material contamination, a phenomenon that is commonly reported in GC-MS studies, and had no impact on the confirmation of the production of biogas. (Gallego et al., 2015). Collectively, the results from the GC-MS supported the observations made during the physical tests and also during flame tests, and this represented good analytical validation of biogas formation in the portable digester.

The results of this work support the theory that decentralized and portable anaerobic digesters can be viable alternatives to conventional large-scale biogas plants with their advantages including the reduced infrastructural needs, ease of operation and the localization of waste to energy (Nobre et al., 2026) In addition to the technical feasibility of the system, it favours sustainable waste management and renewable energy production for contributing to SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), and SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Beings) through clean energy access and better sanitation practices. (Agbakwuru et al., 2024b)

In shadow of this, present portable anaerobic digester is a viable, scalable and environmentally sustainable solution for small-scaled biogas production from cattle dung. Future research can possibly be to optimize operational parameters and gas yield and methane content and to measure the long term performance for better applicability of this system under various field conditions (Abbas et al., 2020)

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